

Original Article

ADULT LITERACY PROGRAMME A TOOL IN PROMOTING COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

This study researched into the Role of Adult Literacy in Promoting Community Development in Enugu State. The study delved into the definition of Adult Literacy, Community, types of community and community development. The purpose of the study was specifically to examine how Adult Literacy can contribute to promoting community development and also identify the challenges hindering Adult Literacy Programs in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study. Survey research design was used. The population of the study was 846 facilitators while a random sampling technique was used to get the sample size of 214 respondents. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire which was validated by three experts one in measurement and evaluation department and two from Continuing Education and development Studies of Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of science and Technology, Agbani. The results of the findings revealed that Adult Education is a good instrument for promoting Community Development. The conclusion was that Adult Literacy Programs should be enhanced so that Community Development can be achieved. The recommendations were that Adult Literacy Programs should be funded regularly and that enlightenment campaign on the awareness of the importance of Adult Education should be intensified by both the government and the stakeholders in Enugu State.

Keywords: *Literacy, Adult literacy, Community, Community Development*

Introduction

Literacy has been recognized to be an important channel by which a country can attain development. This is because it has a great impact on individuals' success and the ability of the person to participate effectively in one's community. Therefore, adult literacy is a programme that aims at improving the

learning ability of an individual. It can take an adequate care of socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems of adults in a community (Odenigbo, 2017). The above statement shows that Adult Literacy is a key to improve health, nutrition, promote skilled manpower, better life style and values brings empowerment, industrialization

and overall development to a community as stated by (Ozoemena, 2013). It cuts across all sectors of human endeavor, such as farms, commerce, Business and so on. This statement shows that Adult Literacy is a very important key in community development because it will exert enormous influence on the smaller society in terms of community development. Community is referred to as a place where a group of people are living together in the same area, sharing the same language, culture, tradition, religion, and bond by a common legal and administrative system or authority. A community is the people who reside in that place, and have the common features that distinguish them from other communities. United Nation (UN) 1963 cited in Ojukwu (2013) stated that community is a process by which the efforts of the people themselves are united with those of governmental (and perhaps non-governmental) authorities to improve the economics, social and cultural conditions of communities, to integrate these community into the life of the nation, and to enable them to contribute fully to national development. Many types of community exists, such as: urban community- this type is located in the towns or cities. Rural community –this is found in remote settings, most of the people in this types are mainly farmers. Small community- this type is known to be very small in all respects, such as in terms of space, population, needs and aspirations. Other ones are medium and large communities, religions communities, secular community, and ethnic community and so on. All these communities needs development .This is because development is a process of social change in a society and it is intended to bring about both social and material advancement for people by allowing them to gain greater control over their environment. Therefore, community development as stated by David, (2018) is a process which involves progression for conditions or state to the next level. It lays more emphasis on the improvement of the people, both

socially and psychologically. Oduaran (1994) cited in Ojukwu (2013) opined that community development is a planned and organized efforts to assist individuals to acquire attitudes, skills and concepts required for their democratic participation in the effective solution to as wide as possible range of community problems in an order of priority determined by their increasing levels of competence. Adult Literacy will be of great use in Enugu State towards achievement of community development. Adult literacy is a programme where the adults who could not attend formal education system are engaged in learning how to read or write and compute numeracy. These programmes helps the adults to learn how to improve themselves economically, socially, culturally, politically and even towards healthy living. It helps to promote improved skilled manpower which will enhance empowerment and industrialization processes in the State. Hence, this programme will expose the people of Enugu State to acquire special skills towards maintaining good health, welfare, agriculture, industry, recreating, among others. This knowledge could be integrated to promote the development of people and their communities. Adult Literacy programmes can be useful in solving different communities' needs in Enugu State such as those that arose due to local challenges and those that were posed mainly by modernization (economic, scientific, material and technological challenges). This can be by the provision of skills, competencies and the modification of behaviours, values attitudes, morals, beliefs, exposure to cooperative practice which will bring in the dynamics of change to the communities. Other challenges are that people are deprived of the basic needs of life such as clothing, houses, medical care, communications, education, transport facilities, recreation, neighborhood amenities, credit facilities and horizon for self-improvement. Hence, the lives of these people living in communities are characterized by poverty, misery

and underdevelopment. Their income remains low and agriculture which is their major occupation has been on the decline because of lack of mechanization and even funds. Nevertheless, whatever the situation, adult literacy programmes can promote community development in Enugu State through improving the life of individuals and groups.

Statement of the Problem

Every Nation’s development lies on the level of Education of its citizens. This is because when communities are full of literates, there will be increase in Gross National Profit (GNP) of that nation because the communities are educated. But when communities are full of illiterates or semi illiterates, there will be no opportunity to achieve (GNP) because those in the communities who are to assist in achieving it are not educated. They are not developed educationally hence, community development is not going to be possible. Therefore, Adult Literacy Programme plays a major role in promoting community development. These reasons bring about the urge to research into this topic “The Role of Adult Literacy in Promoting Community Development in Enugu State”.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

- 1) To examine how adult literacy has contributed in promoting community development in Enugu State.

Research Question 1: How has Adult Literacy Programme contributed to promoting community development in Enugu State?

- 2) To identify the challenges hindering literacy programme from promoting community development in Enugu State.

Research Question

These research questions are generated in line with research objectives as follows:

1. What are the contributions of Adult Literacy Programmes in promoting Community Development in Enugu State?
2. What are the challenges hindering Adult Literacy programmes from promoting community development in Enugu State.

Method

The research design used was survey. The population of the study comprises 846 facilitators from the adult literacy centres in five local government areas of Enugu State. A simple random sampling technique was used to draw Two hundred and fourteen (214) respondents. Two research questions guided the study. A structured questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection and was validated by experts in Adult Education and Measurement and evaluation Departments of Enugu State University of Science and Technology Agbani. The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the facilitators who filled and return them. The data collected were analyzed using statistical method involving frequency and percentage results.

S/N	Items Available	Response	Frequency	Percentage%
1	Adult Literacy Programmes help to promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth	Agree Disagree	174 40	81 19
2	Adult Literacy Programmes promote a productive and decent work for all	Agree Disagree	153 61	71 29

3	Adult Literacy Programmes promote peaceful and inclusive societies for a sustainable community development	Agree Disagree	121 93	57 43
4	Adult Literacy Programmes Provides access to justice for all, build effective accountable, transparent and inclusive institution at all levels.	Agree Disagree	172 42	80 20
5	Adult Literacy Programmes makes the learners to be self-reliant for a solid and sustainable community development	Agree Disagree	123 91	57 43

In item 1 of table 1, 174 out of 214 of the respondents representing 81% agreed with the statement that Adult Literacy Programmes can help to promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth while only 40 respondents representing 19% disagreed. In item 2 of table 1, 153 respondents representing 71% agreed that Adult Literacy Programmes promotes a productive employment and decent work for all while 61 respondents representing 29% disagreed. In item 3 of table 1, 121 respondents representing 57% agreed that ADL programmes promotes peaceful and inclusive

societies for a sustainable community development while 93 respondents representing 43% disagreed. In item 4 of table 1, 172 respondents representing 80% agreed that ADL programmes provide access to justice for all and build effective accountable, transparent and inclusive institution at all levels while 42 respondents representing 20% disagreed. In items 5, 123 respondents representing 57% agreed that ADL programmes makes the learners to be self-reliant for a solid and sustainable community development while 91 respondents representing 43% disagreed.

Research Questions 2: What are the challenges that have being hindering Adult Literacy in Promoting Community Development in Enugu State?

S/N	Items Available	Response	Frequency	Percent %
	The Challenges hindering Adult Literacy from Promoting Community Development in Enugu State are:			
1	Lack of Understanding of the importance of the programme	Agree Disagree	171 43	80 20
2	Lack of Funds to pay the instructors' stipends regularly	Agree Disagree	116 98	54 46
3	Inadequate facilities such as Infrastructures, electricity and other amenities.	Agree Disagree	125 89	58 42
4	Lack of Professional training for the facilitators/instructors in order to be performing better in the class.	Agree Disagree	174 40	81 19

5	Unavailability of teachers aids and instructional materials for the instructors	Agree	118	55
		Disagree	96	45

In item 1 of table 2, 171 respondents representing 80% agreed that lack of understanding of the importance of ADL programmes hinders the programme while 43 respondents representing 20% disagreed. In item 2 of table 2, 116 respondents representing 54% agreed that lack of funds to pay the instructors' stipends regularly also can hinder ADL programmes in Enugu State. While 98 respondents representing 46% disagreed. In item 3 of table 2, 125 respondents representing 58% agreed to the fact that inadequate facilities such as infrastructures electricity and other amenities can hinder the ADL programmes from promoting Community Development (CD) while 89 respondents representing 42% disagreed. In item 4 of table 2, 174 respondents representing 81% agreed that lack of professional training for the facilitators/instructors can hinders ADL programme from promoting Community Development while 40 respondents representing 19% disagreed. Finally, in item 5 of item 2, 118 agreed that unavailability of teachers aids and other instructional material can hinder ADL programmes from promoting Community Development while 96 respondents representing 45% disagreed.

Discussion of Results

The results from the analysis revealed that development potentials of Adult Literacy to Community Development were discovered. The result of the findings reveals that all the developmental potentials were agreed upon as capability of the programme towards ensuring community development through extension services as it helps in ending hunger, achieve food security and improve nutrition and promote mechanized agriculture, ensure inclusive and equitable quality education, and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, reduces or eradicate poverty to enhance community development, promotes

sustained inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, promotes peaceful inclusive societies, provides access to justice for all and build effective accountable and transparent institutions at all levels, makes learners self-reliant and ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages. This is in line with Odenigbo (2017) which stated that ADL programme can take an adequate care of socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems of adults in a community. The result of the findings is also in line with David (2018) which stated that ADL programme is an important key in community Development because it will exert enormous influence on the smaller society, and that it is also a key to improve health, nutrition promotes skill manpower brings empowerment and industrialization and over all development to a Community. Opinions of the respondents sampled revealed that various challenges that hinder ADL programmes were lack of understanding of the importance of ADL Programmes lack of funds, inadequate facilities, lack of professional training for facilitators and unavailability of teachers aids and instructional materials for facilitators/instructors. The above identified challenges are among those listed by Odenigbo 2017. Therefore, this result has revealed the challenges of ADL programmes in promoting Community Development these challenges should be looked into and be addressed urgently.

Conclusion:

This research studied the role of Adult Literacy Programmes in promoting community development in Enugu State. The results of the finding revealed that ADL programmes can contribute to community development if well planned and organized in such a way that the members of the community can have easy access to it.

Recommendations

1. Enlightenment campaign should be intensified on the importance of Education
2. Adult Literacy centers should be funded regularly
3. There should be provision of equipment ,infrastructures and other learning facilities in the centres

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4. Non-governmental Organization (NGOs) and other agencies should always support in funding, providing learning and infrastructural needs that will make adult literacy programmes effective for community development.
5. Seminars/workshops should always be organized by all stakeholders to sensitize and enrich learners and the instructors.
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